

Extraction of Cerium(IV) by Liquid Cation Exchanger (Versatic 10) and its Separation from Lanthanide Elements

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A rapid and selective method for the extraction of cerium(IV) at milligram level with liquid cation exchanger, Versatic 10, in benzene was proposed. Quantitative extraction was achieved in the pH range 5.0-5.5. The effect of variables such as pH of the aqueous phase, diluent, contact time and extractant concentration on the extraction was studied. The equilibration between the two phases was achieved within one minute. The probable composition of the extracted species being CeR_4 , was deduced from the extraction data. The presence of magnesium, calcium, cobalt, nickel, zinc, cadmium and mercury did not interfere in the extraction of cerium(IV). Cerium(IV) was quantitatively separated from several binary and ternary mixtures containing rare earth elements.

VERSATIC acids, viz., Versatic 911, Versatic 10 etc., have been shown to be promising extractants for large scale hydrometallurgical processing of divalent metals^{1,2}. The composition of the extracted species of several metals using Versatic 911 and Versatic 10 were investigated by several workers³⁻⁶. These acids were extensively used in our laboratory for the extraction of di, tri and tetra valent metals⁷⁻⁹. However, no systematic attempt has yet been made to study the extraction behaviour of Ce(IV) with Versatic 10 and hence the title investigation. This offers a simple, rapid and selective method for the extraction and separation of cerium(IV) from lanthanide elements at milligram level. The proposed method is more selective than the methods reported earlier.

The extraction of metals by carboxylic acid takes place by a cation exchange mechanism. This can simply be expressed as :

Barred species are in the organic phase.

Experimental

Apparatus : Elico pH meter (ELICO, Model LI-10, Hyderabad, India) was used for the measurement of pH. Separatory funnels (250 ml) were used for extraction experiments.

Reagents : Versatic 10 (purity, 99%) is a mixture of C_{10} isomeric tertiary monocarboxylic acid¹⁰. It is manufactured and supplied by Shell Co. Ltd. (London) and was used without further purification.

Ceric sulphate solution (3.75 mg/ml) was prepared by dissolving about 3.0 g of $Ce(SO_4)_2 \cdot 4H_2O$ (Chemapol, Czechoslovakia) in 200 ml of double deionised water to which 2 ml of concentrated H_2SO_4 (A. R.) was added. The solution was standardised by the complexometric titration with EDTA using xylenol orange indicator¹¹.

Ascorbic acid (B. D. H., A. R.) was used for the reduction of cerium(IV) during estimation. All other chemicals and solvents used were of analytical grade.

Buffer solutions of different pH were prepared from 1 M sodium acetate solution and the pH were adjusted using chloroacetic acid (pH 1.5 to 2.5) and glacial acetic acid (pH 3.5 to 6).

General extraction procedure : The procedure of the experiment was based on solvent extraction technique. An aliquot (2 ml) of the test solution containing 7.5 mg of the metal ion was mixed in a 250 ml separatory funnel with 10 ml of buffer solution. Sodium hydroxide solution was used for the adjustment of pH. The total volume of the aqueous phase was made 20 ml so that the ultimate concentration of cerium(IV) in the aqueous phase was 2.3×10^{-3} M. The solution was equilibrated with 10 ml of 0.887 M Versatic 10 in benzene for 5 min. The equilibration time was varied from 0.5-10 min and it was found that distribution coefficient reached a constant value within 1 min. However, the equilibration time was fixed to 5 min. All the experiments were carried out at $30 \pm 1^\circ$. The phases, after equilibration, were allowed to settle for 10 min, the aqueous phase separated and equilibrium pH measured. The aqueous phase was washed with benzene (5 ml) to remove the entrained solvent and the amount of cerium(IV) present in that phase was estimated by complexometric titration. The extracted cerium from the organic phase was stripped with 2 N nitric acid (20 ml) for 5 min and finally estimated by EDTA titration. Variations in procedure are indicated at appropriate places.

Results and Discussion

Effect of variables on the extraction :

pH : The extraction of cerium(IV) with Versatic 10 at various pH was performed using buffer solution of different pH. The results (Table 1) showed

that the extraction of cerium(IV) increases with increased pH of the aqueous phase and became quantitative at pH 5.0-5.5. It was observed that under ordinary experimental condition (in absence of acetate buffer) cerium(IV) starts hydrolysis at pH 4.0 which leads to difficulty in phase separation. This tendency was checked upto pH 5.5 by carrying out the extraction in presence of acetate buffer. For all quantitative extraction the pH of aqueous phase was maintained at 5.0.

TABLE 1—EXTRACTION OF CERIUM(IV) AS A FUNCTION OF pH

pH	Extraction of cerium(IV), %	Distribution coefficient D
1.7	0.9	0.02
2.15	3.7	0.08
3.50	40.0	1.89
3.80	78.0	7.09
3.90	87.1	18.50
4.36	95.4	41.48
4.80	97.2	69.43
5.15	98.65	146.1
5.30	99.2	248.0
5.50	99.2	248.0

Various diluents: Cerium was extracted with Versatic 10 solution using various diluents (Table 2). The ratio of organic to aqueous phase was maintained at 1:2. Quantitative extraction of cerium(IV) was achieved in most of the cases. Benzene is the most suitable diluent and was used in all the experiments.

TABLE 2—EFFECT OF DILUENTS ON EXTRACTION OF CERIUM(IV)

Diluent	Dielectric constant	Ce(IV) Extracted, %
Carbon tetrachloride	2.21	97.95
Benzene	2.26	98.9
Xylene	2.35	98.9
Toluene	2.4	97.4
Diisopropyl ether	8.9	Emulsion formation
Chloroform	4.81	97.4
Butanol	16.1	97.95

Equilibration time: The contact time was varied from 30 sec to 10 min. The distribution coefficient reached a constant value within 1 min of shaking and back extraction was completed within 5 min. Contact time and stripping time was kept 5 min in all the experiments. 2 N nitric acid (20 ml) was used for stripping cerium from the organic phase.

Versatic 10 concentration: The effect of extractant concentration on extraction was studied by varying the concentration of Versatic 10 from $3.4 \times 10^{-3} M$ to $1.08 \times 10^{-1} M$ using benzene as diluent. The extraction experiments were carried out at constant metal concentration ($2.3 \times 10^{-3} M$) and constant pH. Plot of log D against log [Versatic 10] produced a straight line of slope = 1.9. Versatic 10 in benzene diluent exists as dimer⁶,

which indicates that four solvent molecules are entering into the extracted species. The probable extraction mechanism may therefore be represented as:

where R_2H_2 represents the dimeric form of Versatic 10 in benzene and barred species are in the organic phase.

Extractive separation: Cerium(IV) was separated from several binary mixtures using the recommended extraction procedure. The aqueous phase, containing $2.3 \times 10^{-3} M$ of cerium(IV) and appropriate quantity of foreign ions, was equilibrated with 0.887 M Versatic 10 (10 ml) in benzene for 5 min at pH 5.0. The organic phase after equilibrium, was stripped with 2 N nitric acid (20 ml) for 5 min and cerium(IV) was estimated by complexometric titration. The amount of foreign ions coextracted with cerium were negligible in most of the cases. Calcium, magnesium, cobalt, nickel, zinc, cadmium and mercury did not interfere in the extraction. Cerium was separated from lanthanum, praseodymium, neodymium, samarium, gadolinium, dysprosium and terbium. The interfering ions are iron, copper, thorium and uranium. The effect of foreign ions and their tolerance limits are shown in Table 3.

TABLE 3—EFFECT OF FOREIGN IONS ON THE EXTRACTION OF CERIUM(IV) WITH VERSATIC 10 (pH 5.0)

Foreign ions	mg	Cerium		Error %
		Taken (mg)	Found (mg)	
Mg ⁺⁺	10.0	7.5	7.44	0.84
Ca ⁺⁺	"	"	7.44	0.84
Co ⁺⁺	"	"	7.44	0.84
Ni ⁺⁺	"	"	7.5	0
Zn ⁺⁺	"	"	7.44	0.84
Cd ⁺⁺	"	"	7.44	0.84
La ⁺⁺	"	"	7.37	1.67
Pr ⁺⁺	"	"	7.44	0.84
Nd ⁺⁺	15.0	"	7.44	0.84
Sm ⁺⁺	8.0	"	7.37	1.67
Gd ⁺⁺	10.0	"	7.44	0.84
Dy ⁺⁺	5.0	"	7.37	1.67
Tb ⁺⁺	5.0	"	7.31	2.50
Hg ⁺⁺	10.0	"	7.46	0.56

Separation of cerium(IV) from synthetic mixtures: The recommended procedure for the extraction of Ce(IV) was applied to several synthetic mixtures produced by mixing 5 mg of each metal ion. The total volume of the aqueous phase was kept 20 ml and extracted with 0.887 M Versatic 10 (10 ml) in benzene. Extractions were carried out at pH 5.1 using suitable buffer solution. The results given in Table 4 show that in most of the cases quantitative recovery of Ce(IV) was achieved. The proposed method can therefore be applied for selective extraction and separation of Ce(IV) from rare earth mixtures present at milligram level. The method is simple and rapid in comparison to other methods reported earlier.

TABLE 4—QUANTITATIVE RECOVERY OF CERIUM(IV) FROM RARE EARTH MIXTURES USING VERSATIC 10 (pH 5.1)

Sample No.	Synthetic mixture	Cerium(IV)		Error %
		Taken (mg)	Found (mg)	
1.	Ce(IV) + La(III) + Pr(III)	7.5	7.5	0
2.	Ce(IV) + Pr(III) + Nd(III)	..	7.5	0
3.	Ce(IV) + Nd(III) + Sm(III)	..	7.48	0.2
4.	Ce(IV) + Sm(III) + Gd(III)	..	7.42	1.0
5.	Ce(IV) + Gd(III) + Tb(III)	..	7.44	0.84
6.	Ce(IV) + Tb(III) + Dy(III)	..	7.41	0.81
7.	Ce(IV) + La(III) + Pr(III) + Nd(III)	..	7.42	1.0

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